

Work Life Balance among Women Employees with Reference to Teaching Faculties at KLE S.Nijalingappa College

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Life is like riding a bicycle to keep your balance you keep moving- Albert Einstein

ABSTRACT

In modern world women have shouldered equal responsibilities with men for the welfare of the family in various ways. Historically women in India were revered and the birth of a girl was widely believed to mark the arrival of Lakshmi – the Goddess of wealth and riches. But today's women are working in various areas and they are also a part of the bread-winner to their family. Women's life is a mixture of various roles; Most of the women are doing the best to balance their work, family and service. This research article identifies certain factors that strongly impact the work life balance (WLB) of female professors in KLE S. NIJALINGAPPA COLLEGE at RAJAJINAGAR, BANGALORE. The study highlights the various factors and challenges which have an effect on the professional and personal lives of 45 female teachers working at KLE SNC. This paper highlights the various personal and professional factors which affects the work-life balance of women employees. The study highlights the various challenges and issues faced by Women employees to achieve WLB. The study suggests that there is a need for the institution to initiate work life balance programs for employee satisfaction and to improve the performance of employees. The study also suggest that the management should take steps to brings down the overtime workings hours for enhancing quality in teaching and also focus more on teaching rather than administrative work.

Keywords: *work life balance, women, employee satisfaction, personal and professional factors*

INTRODUCTION:

Work life balance is the idea which is related with well balancing between your work and lifestyle. It is a proper management of your career and personal life. The biggest challenge for women is how to balance the demands of family and career. Women are getting into jobs and they continue to work even after marriage. A married woman has more responsibility than man in taking care of young children and family. Work Life Balance of Women employee has become an important subject since the women are equally sharing the earning responsibility for the betterment of their family. The working women efficiently overcome difficult situations by their commitment and perseverance. The participation of women in income generation activities lends them to satisfy their home needs to a greater extent.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE:

Number of studies has addressed this issue in different perspectives. Some of the papers related to this subject are reviewed.

Baruch and Barnett found that women who had multiple life roles (e.g., mother, wife, employee) were

less depressed and had higher self-esteem than women who were more satisfied in their marriages and jobs compared to women and men who were not married, unemployed, or childless.

Santhana lakshmi and sujata Gopinath (March 2013), Work life balance of women employees among teaching faculties in SRM school of management, Tamilnadu. The study examined that married women are more affected and their work life balance is severely distorted. The study also found that some of the married women mainly work for financial reasons. This study finds the various factors which affect their work-life balance, and methods to carry out to achieve the same.

Tapasya Julka and Urvika Mathur (February 2017), A Conceptual Study of Work-Life Balance among Women employee. The study examined that the effect of work-life balance on the quality of life of married working women.

Work Life balance is not something that just happens. It involves the efforts of a number of partners: the employee, the organization for which the employee works, the family with whom the employee lives and the society in which all are embedded. It involves mutual understanding and respect between all of these players. (N.Gayathri & Dr.P.Karthikeyan, August 2013).

Challenges faced by working women:

Comparisons of stress with women work-life and women work in various era's:

<i>The changing Equations of New Era</i>			
<i>The Changing Equations</i>			
	The Machine Age	The Industrial Age	The Networked Age
Stress	High	Higher	Highest
Work-Life balance	You went to work-life started only when you go home	Not only are people working at work, but also at home	24-hour workdays split into compartments dedicated for 'life'
Women and Work	The men worked and women tended the house	Both men and women worked, and women still tended the house	Both men and women work and tend to the house

By overcoming all those challenges and stress, women has to excel in career and even in their family life. Modern women needs physically and mentally to be strong. She had lot of roles to play even in family life. One of the biggest challenges is child care. Working women has to leave their kids in day care that gives lot of mental stress to them.

Women's work life balance needs = Healthy life + satisfaction in both professional and personal

OBJECTIVES:

- To study how nature of family structure or personal factor influence stress in work place
- To identify various professional factors that affect their personal life
- To understand the various ways carried by women to achieve their work life balance.
- To study about the satisfaction level of employees in work life balance.

PERIOD OF THE STUDY:

The period of the study was from March to April 2017.

The primary data was collected by distributing a questionnaire among the teaching faculties, those who are from different department of KLE S.NIJALINGAPPA COLLEGE, Rajajinagar, Bangalore, India

RESEARCH QUESTIONS:

- Demographic details like Age, Experience & Marital status.
- Factors that motivate you to work
- How many hours in a day do you spend with your family.
- Rate the personal factors that affect professional life
- Rate the professional factors that affect your personal life
- How often do you think or worry about work
- Do you ever miss out any quality time with your family or your friends because of pressure
- How do you manage stress arising from your work.
- How much you are satisfied with your work life balance provided by the organization
- Do you think that work life balance will improve the organization effectiveness
- Rate the options that you prefer from your institution for your work life balance

SAMPLE:

- Primary data was collected from the faculty members of KLE S.NIJALINGAPPA COLLEGE, Rajajinagar, Bangalore, India
- Sample size is 45. Convenience sampling were used for the study.
- Questionnaire was distributed to the teaching faculties belonging to various disciplines.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY:

- Research design proposed for the study is 'Descriptive' type of research service. This type of research deals with quality of responses from the respondents, attitudes, interests, technical skills, experience, behavioral, beliefs and values, emotions, personality, self-concept etc.,
- Primary data was collected by questionnaire survey method.

- Secondary data was collected from journals and Research articles to support the research.

Family Structure

Sl.No	Family structure	No of respondents	Percentage
1	Joint	13	29%
2	Nuclear	32	71%

Interpretation: 71% of the respondents are living in nuclear family.

No. of years working in the same organization:

Sl.No	No of years working	No of respondents	Percentage
1	1 year	13	29%
2	Between 1-5	12	27%
3	5-10 years	10	18%
4	More than 10	12	26%

Interpretation: Most of the respondents have 1 year of experience in KLE S. Nijalingappa College.

Marital Status:

Sl.No	Marital Status	No of respondents	Percentage
1	Married	35	78%
2	Unmarried	10	22%

Interpretation: 78% of the respondents are married.

Number of children:

Sl.No	Number of children	No of respondents	Percentage
1	No Children	18	43%
2	1 Child	17	40%
3	2 Children	10	17%

Interpretation: 18 % of the respondents do not have children.

Factors that motivate you to work.

Sl.No	Factors	1	2	3	4	5	Total
1	Personal satisfaction	13	6	5	5	16	45
2	Economic Independence	8	9	11	10	7	45
3	Support to family	9	10	9	8	9	45
4	Social recognition	7	14	8	8	8	45
5	Service to society	12	10	5	8	10	45

Applying weighted average method

Ranks	First	Second	Third	Fourth	Fifth
Weights	5	4	3	2	1

Opinion/Rank	1	2	3	4	5	Total	Weight	Rank
Personal satisfaction	65	24	15	10	16	130	8.66	5
Economic Independence	40	36	33	20	7	136	9.06	4
Support to family	45	40	27	16	9	137	9.13	3
Social recognition	35	56	24	16	8	139	9.26	2
Service to society	60	40	15	16	10	141	9.4	1

Interpretation:

It is inferred that majority of the respondents feel that service to the society motivates them to work.

➤ **Hours spent with your family**

Hours	No of respondents	Percentage
Less than 2 hours	2	4%
2-3 hours	3	7%
3-4 hours	8	18%
4-5 hours	14	31%
More than 5 hours	18	40%

Interpretation: 40% of the respondents spend more than 5 hours with their family.

➤ **How often do you think or worry about work**

Contents	No of respondents	Percentage
Frequently	12	27%
Sometimes	20	44%
Occasionally	7	16%
Rarely	2	4%
Never	4	9%

Interpretation: 44% of respondents sometimes worry about work.

➤ **Do you ever miss out any quality time with your family or your friends because of pressure?**

Contents	No of respondents	Percentage
Never	2	4%
Rarely	7	16%
Sometimes	20	44%
Often	13	29%
Always	3	7%

Interpretation: 44% of respondents sometimes miss out quality time with their family.

➤ **How do you manage stress arising from your work?**

Methods to manage	No of respondents	Percentage
Yoga	1	2%
Meditation	6	13%
Entertainment	11	25%
Dance	1	2%
Music	21	47%
Others	5	11%

Interpretation: 47% of the respondents listen to music to manage stress.

➤ **Personal factor that affect the professional life**

Factors/opinion	Strongly agree%	Agree%	Neutral%	Disagree%	Strongly Disagree%
Children development	15.5	31.1	31.1	13.3	8.9
Attitude of spouse/family members	6.6	26.6	22.2	31.1	13.3
Family emergencies/events	22.2	28.8	28.8	4.4	15.5
Health issues	22.2	31.1	11.1	17.8	17.8

Interpretation:

Majority of the respondents strongly agree that family emergencies and health issues affect their professional life.

➤ **Professional factor that affect your personal life**

Factors	Strongly agree%	Agree%	Neutral%	Disagree%	Strongly Disagree%
Long working hours	26.6	33.3	17.8	8.9	13.3
Long travelling hours to work place	31.1	24.4	20	15.5	8.9
Attitude of superiors	13.3	26.6	33.3	17.8	8.9
Work on holidays	33.3	33.3	15.5	6.7	11.1

Interpretation:

Majority of the respondents strongly agree that work on holidays & long travelling hours to work place affect their personal life.

➤ **How much you are satisfied with your work life balance provided by the organization.**

Contents	No of respondents	Percentage
Highly satisfied	3	7%
Satisfied	22	49%
Neutral	15	33%
Dissatisfied	4	9%
Highly dissatisfied	1	2%

Interpretation: 49% of respondents are satisfied with the work life balance provided by the organization.

➤ **Do you think that work life balance will improve the organization effectiveness?**

Contents	No of respondents	Percentage
Yes	41	91%
No	4	9%

Interpretation: 91% of respondents think work life balance will improve the organization effectiveness.

➤ **Rank the expectations from the institution for maintaining work life balance**

Options/Rank	1	2	3	Total
Less work pressure	13	27	5	45
Salary	8	27	10	45
Interpersonal Relationship	17	23	5	45
Recreational facilities	10	19	16	45

➤ **Applying weighted average method**

Ranks	First	Second	Third
Weights	3	2	1

Opinion/Rank	1	2	3	Total	Weight	Rank
Less work pressure	39	54	5	98	16.33	2
Salary	24	54	10	88	14.66	3
Interpersonal Relationship	51	46	5	102	17	1
Recreational facilities	30	38	16	84	14	4

Interpretation: Majority of respondents expects that interpersonal relationship helps to maintain work life balance.

FINDINGS:

- 71% of the respondents are living in nuclear family and 78% of the respondents are married.
- It is inferred that majority of the respondents feel that service to the society motivates them to work in teaching profession.
- 40% of the respondents spend more than 5 hours with their family.
- 47% of the respondents listen to music to manage stress.
- Majority of the respondents strongly agree that family emergencies and health issues affect their professional life
- Majority of the respondents strongly agree that work on holidays & long travelling hours to work place affect their personal life.
- 49% of respondents are satisfied with the work life balance provided by the organization.
- 91% of respondents think work life balance will improve the organization effectiveness.
- Majority of respondents expects that interpersonal relationship in work place helps to maintain work life balance

SUGGESTIONS:

To make effective work-life balance strategies and efforts has to be done from management as well as faculties.

FOR EMPLOYEES:

Planning and personal effort is important for balance in work and personal life. Management can only facilitate work life balance with many schemes that can attract employees and satisfy their needs but it is employees, who have to plan, prioritize and schedule their work and life obligations.

FOR EMPLOYERS:

Institutions need to create counselling services in their respective organizations by appointing full time counsellors who can help employees in balancing their mental and physical issues.

Management need to organise some recreational activities which help them to manage stress and to develop interpersonal relationship between employees and employer.

CONCLUSION:

From the above discussion, it is logical to conclude that both of them like institutions as well as staff members should plan and organize the things to address their work life balance issues. Organisations need to adopt some human resource strategies and policies to overcome the issues of the work life balance of women especially in educational institutions, to support their teaching staff in managing their work life balance which would increase the staff performance as well as organization effectiveness.

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